

Improvement in Adhesive Property of Polyolefins, Silicone Resin, and Other Stable Polymeric Materials

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1 Introduction

Polyolefins such as polypropylene (PP) and polyethylene (PE) are extensively used because of the excellent chemical and physical properties and low price. Recently, ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) attracts much attention, because of the high tensile strength and high wear resistance. However, polyolefins have no hydrophilic property and no bonding property. If their surface property is improved well, they can be used more extensively. Techniques such as a polymer-blend method, a corona-discharge treatment, [1] an ozone treatment, [2] a plasma treatment, [3,4] UV-irradiation [5,6], a graft polymerization [7-9], and chemical treatments with sulfuric acid, hydro fluoride and other reagents were carried out to improve the surface property of polyolefin materials. In addition, PP non-woven fabrics were treated with hydrophilic resin in the presence of persulfate salts. [10] Polymeric materials including polyolefins were coated with polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), [11] or coated with polymer mixtures with or without some additives and some binders containing polymers after corona or plasma treatments. [12,13] However, the improved property does not give high durability, because these processes are only a polymer coating which forms no chemical bonds between polymeric materials and coated polymers.

We found that the combination of several conventional methods was effective for the modification of polyolefins, and prepared polypropylene fabrics which absorb water. Improving the technique, polyethylene and polypropylene materials could be bonded to other materials such as wood, aluminum plates with general adhesives. The present method can be applied for the modification of other stable polymeric materials such as polycarbonate (PC), silicone and fluorine resins. The polymeric materials improved by the present method are useful for preparing composite materials. [14]

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Polymeric materials: PP non-woven fabrics (unit weight 50g/m²), PP plates, UHMWPE (average molecular weight 5,000,000-8,000,000) plates (unit weight 467g /m²) and films (thickness 60, 100μm, weight 30, 83 g /m²), PET films (weight 72g /m²), PC plates, silicone resins and fluorine resins (PTFE, PETFE, etc.), etc. were used.

Adhesives: commercial polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) glue, starch glue, polyvinylacetate (PVAC)-PVA mixture, polycyanoacrylate (PCA), epoxy resin bond were used to examine the adhesive property of modified polymeric materials.

Paint: commercial water-based paint (Asahipen, Co. Ltd. Japan) which contains synthetic resins (acrylic, silicone and fluorine resins), pigments and organic solvents was used. The peeling test of the coated paint was carried out by the cross-cut test, JIS K5400.

2.2 Treatment

Polymeric materials were activated by chemical oxidation, or energy irradiations such as UV, plasma, high-voltage electric discharge treatment. Activated polymeric materials were subsequently treated with a solution of polymers, monomers or other chemical reagents in the presence of catalysts or initiators. Catalysts or initiators such as benzoyl peroxide, cerium ammonium nitrate (IV), potassium or ammonium persulfates, hydrogen peroxide, inorganic reductants of copper salts, iron salts, sodium hydrogen sulfite, sodium thiosulfate, dialkyl peroxide, diacyl peroxides and other usual initiators for radical polymerization, etc. were used.

A polymeric material is taken out of the reaction mixture and washed with solvents or detergent solutions.

2.3 Measurements

A bonding strength of polymeric materials bonded to other materials was measured by a tensile tester, Shimadzu AGS-H5KN. The three-point bending test was carried out to observe the breaking of FRPs.

Infrared (IR) spectra of polymeric materials are obtained by an ATR method using a Shimadzu IR Prestige-21 equipped with an ATR accessory, Smiths DuraSampl IR II.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Activation Process

Polymeric materials are oxidized in the course of the activation treatment. IR spectra of untreated PP and treated PP oxidized in the activation process were obtained by the ATR method of FTIR. The treated PP gives an absorption peak based on carbonyl groups at around 1730 cm^{-1} . The relative peak area at around 1730 cm^{-1} against the treatment time gave a straight line. The activation process was made only on the surface area of materials in order to avoid the degradation. When thick polymeric materials were treated, the degradation could be negligible.

Figure 1 gives the ATR-IR spectra of original (untreated) UHMWPE plate and the UHMWPE plate treated by UV irradiation. The absorption at 1727 cm^{-1} is considered to be due to carbonyl groups. The untreated UHMWPE seems to be oxidized to some extent. The absorbance at 1727 cm^{-1} increased after the activation process.

Fig.1 ATR-IR spectra of UHMWPE plates; untreated one (bottom) and treated one (top).

3.2 Treatment with Reagents and Reaction Mechanism

Polymeric materials treated by the activation process were reacted with various kinds of chemical compounds. When PP plates were reacted with acrylic esters (monomers), the graft polymer was observed by IR spectroscopy. The reaction mechanism is speculated, considering the references. [15] The mechanism is given in Scheme 1. Polymeric materials are oxidized in the activation process and hydroperoxyl groups are formed. As the groups are not stable, some of them might be changed to the other functional groups. These groups are considered to react with chemical reagents (P).

Scheme 1 Mechanism

3.2 Water Absorption Property

Modified PP fabrics gave a durable hydrophilic property. PP non-woven fabrics absorbed water of about ten times of the original weight. On the other hand, an untreated PP fabric gives a high water repellency. Figure 2 gives photographs of untreated and modified PP fabrics. The modified PP gave a high water absorption property after dipping in an aqueous KOH solution (conc. 20 wt.%) for 14 days at $40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The water absorption property was maintained well after boiling in aqueous detergent solutions. This property is preferable for the use in battery separators.

Fig.2 Untreated (left) and modified PP fabrics sprinkled with water.

3.3 Improvement of Adhesive Property

The adhesive property of polymeric materials was improved by the present method. Figure 3 gives the modified UHMWPE plate bonded to a wooden plate and an aluminum plate. Figure 4 gives a specimen of PP plate bonded to an acrylic resin plate which was examined by the tensile strength test. The material failure was observed in the tensile shear test of the modified PP and UHMPE plates bonded to other materials such as acrylic resin, wood, and aluminum plates. Figure 5 gives a modified fluorine resin bonded to a rubber plate.

Fig.3 UHMPE bonded to wood and aluminum plates.

Fig.4 Specimen of PP plate bonded to acrylic resin after the tensile shear test

Fig.5 Fluorine resin (white part) bonded to rubber plate

3.4 Improvement in Application Property of Water-based Paint Coating

Treated PE, UHMWPE, PP, PC, PET, silicone and fluorine resins, etc. were improved in the application

property of water-based paint coating. Figure 6 gives the result of the cross-cut test for PP plate coated with water-based acrylic paint. The upper specimen gives a PP plate treated incompletely and the lower one modified well. The lower PP gave full-mark, 100/100 in the cross-cut test. Figure 7 gives an untreated PE ball (the lower left), an untreated and painted PE ball (the upper left) and modified and painted balls (the right two). Figure 8 gives untreated (left) and modified UHMWPE plates coated with water-based acrylic paint.

Fig.6 Cross-cut test of PP plates coated with water-based paint

Fig.7 PE balls coated with water-based paint

Fig.8 Cross-cut test of untreated (upper) and modified (under) UHMWPE plates coated with water-based acrylic paint

Fig.9 Silicone resin plates coated with water-based paint; untreated one (left), modified one (right)

3.5 Application of Modified PP Fiber on Composite Materials

As modified PP fibers could be bonded to epoxy resin without adhesives, they were useful for filler fibers in FRP. Specimens of composite materials (FRPs) were prepared by mixing untreated or modified PP fibers in epoxy resin. In comparison, composite materials were prepared by mixing usual carbon fiber or glass fiber as fillers in epoxy resin. These composite materials showed the different way of breaking in the three-point bending test. The FRP with modified PP fiber was not divided into two pieces after the breaking; the modified PP fibers were not separated completely from the epoxy resin. On the other hand, the FRPs made with carbon fiber or glass fiber were broken into two pieces. Figure 10 gave the specimens used in the three-point bending test; the left one was made with untreated PP fiber and epoxy resin, and the right, modified PP and epoxy resin.

3.6 Solvent Bonding

Fig.10 FRP specimens after the three-point bending test; untreated PP (left), and modified PP (right)

Modified silicone rubber tube could be connected strongly to modified PP tube without adhesives. Figure 11 gives silicone rubber tube bonded to PP tube (T-tube) with usual organic solvent. This technique is useful for the medical devices.

Fig.11 Silicone rubber tubes bonded to a PP T-tube without adhesives

4. Conclusions

Polymeric materials modified by the present technique showed a good bonding property to other materials with usual adhesives. The modified polymeric materials were improved in the application property of coating with water-based paint. Oil-based paint was also effective for coating the modified materials. The present method enables the bonding of polymeric materials without adhesives. The technique is expected to be useful in many fields.

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